

THE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS OF A CHILD'S SELF-CONCEPTION AND MOTIVATION AREA

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the pre-school education system is further improved as an important link of the integrated continuous education system, and modern educational programs and technologies that develop children intellectually, spiritually, aesthetically and physically are introduced into the educational process. In order to radically increase the level of their school readiness, the process of development of the child's self-awareness and motivational sphere, as well as emotion and its development, are described.

Mental development of a person, his formation as a person is related to the determination of self-awareness, that is, self-awareness as a physical, spiritual and social being.

The development of self-awareness takes place in each child in its own way. However, in all children, usually by the end of the first year of life, there are signs confirming the emergence of self-awareness: the child begins to separate himself, his body from the space that surrounds him. The further development of self-awareness depends on the child's understanding of his own desires and the motives of his activity in general. Understanding the motives of one's activity helps the child to move to the next stage of self-awareness, that is, to be able to separate it from one's own actions.

Initially, the child does not understand himself as a subject of activity. "Daniyor is

jumping", "Sevinch wants to sleep", - children of early childhood say about themselves.

The 3rd year of life is considered an important stage in the development of self-awareness. Because during this period, the child begins to gradually separate the action that he attached to the object. This phenomenon does not happen suddenly. The reason for its implementation is that the child performs the previous subject action in new conditions and transfers it to other subjects. The words "I'm playing", "I'm dressing", "I'm eating" and the word "myself" at the age of 3. we can often meet in the child's speech. One of the most important achievements of early childhood is the transition from expressing oneself with the third person pronoun to using the pronoun "I". Some psychologists (L.I. Bojovich) even believe that the "I" system that appears at the end of early childhood

and the need for independent action that creates it, the need to realize and express one's "I" They believe that it is the most central new structure emerging in the period. Among the structures that arise from this structure, the occurrence of self-evaluation is very important in the development of a child as a person.

In the initial stages of personality formation, that is, in the genesis (emergence) of self-evaluation at the end of early childhood and the beginning of kindergarten, the child's communication with adults is of decisive importance. Because the child does not have adequate knowledge about his capabilities, he accepts the assessment given to him by an adult. In other words, the child evaluates himself through adults, through the opinion of his parents about the child.

In this period, the child relies on the adult's opinion in self-evaluation. The elements of independent self-image appear a little later. According to the special prohibition, (B.G. Nechaev and others) these elements are initially manifested not in the evaluation of personal qualities and moral qualities, but in the evaluation of objective and external characteristics. This shows that the movement is not completely separated from the object.

A very noticeable change in the development of a child's personality at kindergarten age is expressed in the transition from evaluating the external characteristics of another person to evaluating personal characteristics. It is observed that children of all age groups evaluate other people more objectively than themselves. However, there are some differences here. In particular, children of senior kindergarten age "Who is the best child among you?" they usually don't answer "I" to the question. But this does not mean that the child's self-esteem has decreased. The reason kids don't give this answer is because at this age they often learn that it's not okay to brag. If they want to evaluate themselves in a positive way, they often do it indirectly. For example, "Are you a good boy or a bad boy?" children (a large group of kindergarten children) do not answer "Good" or "Bad" to the question, "I don't know... I listen to adults", "I also know how to count to 100", "I always tell the attendants" I will help."

In the kindergarten age, self-evaluation has an emotional character. The child's assessment of others will also have this characteristic. If a child feels trust in any of the adults around him, he will give a positive assessment to that person if he receives affection.

Children of senior kindergarten age try to evaluate the inner world of the adults around them. Unlike children of middle and junior kindergarten age, adults give a much deeper and differentiated assessment of their inner world.

It was found that the child's position in the group affects his self-esteem. For example, there is a tendency for children with a low position in the group to give a very high self-esteem, and on the contrary, for children with a much better position in the group, to have a low self-esteem. By the end of the kindergarten age, the child's assessment of others begins to take on a deeper, more detailed and expanded tone. These changes are explained by the fact that children of senior kindergarten age become more interested in the inner world of people, they learn important criteria for evaluation, and their thinking and speech develop.

The self-esteem of a kindergarten-age child also reflects the feelings of pride and shame that are developing in him. The

development of self-awareness is inextricably linked with the formation of the child's cognitive and motivational spheres. As a result of the development of this area, the child begins to be able to understand both himself and the situation he occupies, that is, the understanding of his social "I" is formed. This phenomenon plays an important role in the child's transition to the next age stage and his psychological readiness for school. By the end of kindergarten age, the child's independence and critical spirit in the assessment of others and himself grows significantly. The motivational field of a child of kindergarten age is actively developing. The behavior of a child at the age of kindergarten is not much different from that of early childhood. Even in this period, children act mainly under the influence of situational emotions and desires, while performing an action, they do not fully understand and cannot explain why they are doing it. My child's behavior in kindergarten age is very clear. Different

motives motivate children at different stages of kindergarten age to do exactly the same action. For example, if a 3-year-old child washes his toys, the goal is to play with water, while a 6-year-old child's goal is to clean his toys and help his mother.

In the kindergarten period, motives specific to this type of behavior appear in the motivational sphere. Among them, there are also motives related to the child's interest in the world of adults and trying to be like them.

Special studies (L.Z.Neverovich, etc.) show that motives that are social in nature have a greater motivating force already in kindergarten, even more than motives such as personal interest and interest in the external, procedural aspects of activity. can have. However, motives that are social in nature and content are formed spontaneously, randomly, not by themselves, but under the educational influence of adults.

So, new motives of behavior appear in kindergarten age. These motives enter into certain mutual relations and form a hierarchy of motives by connecting with each other. The hierarchy of motives is a structure that appears in the motivational field of a child in kindergarten age and occupies a very important place in its development.

Due to the interdependence of motivations in the hierarchy of motives, a child can abandon an activity that seems interesting to him at the moment in order to perform an important, but rather boring task.

During the kindergarten age, the motives of activity fall into a certain system, and some motives begin to prevail over others. The prevailing motive determines the direction of the child's facial expression. Even though the core of the child's personality is just

forming in the kindergarten age, a certain trend in children's behavior begins to be observed during this period. This orientation can be different - from egoistic orientation to individualistic, social orientation (of course, within the scope of this age).

At the kindergarten age, some children show creativity in their behavior, and in some children, the tendency to mischief and consumerism is clearly manifested. Educators and parents should quickly notice such a tendency. Because this gives an opportunity to correct negative traits in time, to form socially valued needs and motives, and to create conditions for self-expression for every child. A child's activity involves various emotions and feelings in the context of his knowledge of the world and himself, relationships with adults and peers. He has a certain attitude towards what he is doing and what he is doing around him. This relationship creates certain emotions and feelings in the child. Emotions and feelings are also a unique form of reality reflection. It is manifested in the child's attitude to the environment, the satisfaction or non-satisfaction of a need, and the inner experiences that arise.

The following general directions of the development of emotions and feelings can be pointed out: the formation of an emotional state depending on the change in the child's life situation; the breakdown of family feelings based on emotions; the formation of emotions and feelings as a new structure among personal structures.

The ontogenesis of emotions and feelings has its own specific laws:

✓ Initially, during ontogenesis, emotions appear that represent ordinary experiences. These experiences arise depending on the satisfaction of my natural

needs (if satisfied - positive, if not satisfied - negative emotions arise). Such emotions also exist in animals. However, the simplest emotions in a child should be distinguished from the simplest emotions in animals. Because the form of manifestation of my emotions has a social character in a person. For a child from the age of 2, reactions expressing joy, happiness, generally positive emotions are considered to be the most informative (giving a lot of information). In one of the experiments, children aged 2-9 were asked to identify different facial reactions (reactions expressing surprise, anger, fear, joy, etc.) from photographs and then show them. It was found out from the experiment that the children were the first to show a facial reaction expressing happiness. So, at first, the ability to recognize and display facial reactions expressing positive emotions, among other reactions, is formed.

The development of emotions and feelings is related to other psbdk processes, especially the development of speech. With the help of speech, the child understands and manages his feelings and emotions. Through speech, children not only express their need for something, but also express their experiences in a certain way.

The development of a child's emotions is related to certain social situations. A child's understanding of the situation, experiencing the situation and changes in it creates a certain emotional state. A change in the child's lifestyle and daily routine can cause the disruption of the usual situation for the child. This sometimes creates stress. According to A.I.Mishkis and L.G.Golubeva, children need 2 months to adapt to new conditions.

Violation of the usual situation can cause affective reactions as well as fear. Affect (a

short-term, intense negative emotional reaction) can also be the result of impaired control function of the cerebral cortex.

Change in children can overcome inhibition. Opposite (negative) emotions may appear due to the fact that the child cannot inhibit the enthusiastic expression of positive emotions. For example, exuberant joy often ends in crying and tears.

In the time structure of a preschool child's activity, the meaning of emotions gradually changes: in the early stages, experiences appear as an emotional assessment of the achieved result, and in the later stages, they appear in the form of emotional perception in advance until the performance of the movement.

L.Z. In the experiment conducted by Neverovich, 4-6 year old children had to pick 19 circles in a certain sequence and make pyramids. Children performed the task well not only when the importance of the task was explained to them (when it was explained that the pyramid was needed to play the game), but also when an emotional perception of the situation was formed in advance. The experimenter shows children pictures to create an emotional perception of the situation in advance. The first picture shows the children crying in front of the spreading circles, and the second one shows the children happily playing with the made pyramids. Discussing pictures with children creates an emotionally colorful picture of the consequences of performing or not performing the given task. This encourages the child to complete the given task to the end.

As written by A. V. Zaporozhes, as the child develops, affective and cognitive processes interact and form a whole functional

system of human emotions. This system allows the subject not only to foresee the consequences of his actions, but also to feel them at the same time, and thus to adequately emotionally control complex forms of activity.

In general, children have an optimistic attitude to life situations, they are characterized by a cheerful, life-satisfied mood. Taking into account the laws of development of emotions and feelings in

the ontogeny, as well as conditions and age characteristics, makes it possible to form psychological readiness for school in children.

One of the main components of psychological preparation for school is emotional preparation. This preparation requires not only to welcome the start of education at school with joy, but also to develop family feelings and emotional characteristics of the child's personality.

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